

ARTIFICIAL MARBLE PRODUCED WITH BIOMASS ASH

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ABSTRACT

In Brazil, the state of Pernambuco stands out nationally in the clothing sector, especially due to industrial activities in the Agreste region. Many laundries use large amounts of firewood monthly to generate steam in boilers, resulting in the production of biomass ash and causing disposal problems due to irregular dumping. An alternative for managing these wastes is to incorporate them into an economically viable production process. Artificial stones, which are highly profitable composites that mimic natural ornamental stones, present a promising solution for the waste from laundry boilers. In this context, the objective of this study is to produce synthetic marble pieces using mesquite wood ash as a filler in a polyester matrix. For this, pieces were developed with 40% mesquite wood ash and 60% by weight of crystal orthophthalic polyester resin, plus 1% catalyst. The material was placed in a metal mold and subjected to constant pressure of 1 ton for 24 hours. The characterization tests included granulometry, X-ray diffraction, apparent density, compressive strength, and flexural strength. The mechanical strength results indicated that the composite material developed is similar to the natural marble described in the literature, demonstrating that the material has great potential for use in civil construction.

KEYWORDS: Ash; Mesquite wood; Synthetic marble; Artificial stone; Composite.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the Agreste region of the State of Pernambuco, particularly in the cities of Caruaru, Toritama, and Santa Cruz do Capibaribe, a thriving and advanced industrial activity is observed in the textile and clothing sectors. The growth of these industries has led to the establishment of industrial laundries in the area, especially in Caruaru. These laundries use water from the Ipojuca River in their operations and consume locally sourced firewood as an energy source [1]. On a daily basis, laundries in the Pernambuco Agreste region generate ashes as a byproduct of burning firewood in their boilers. In many cases, these residues are improperly disposed of, either in the soil or in water bodies. The intensive use of firewood is also common in other productive areas of the state, such as the gypsum industry in Araripe and the ceramic sector, leading to significant ash production by Pernambuco industries. For instance, a medium-sized laundry can produce 6500 kg of ashes monthly [2].

As part of strategies aimed at reducing environmental impact, there is a growing trend towards the reuse of industrial waste. The search for economically viable alternatives has led to the integration of waste into production processes. A common practice today involves incorporating these residues into polymeric matrices, resulting in the formation of composites. This approach contributes not only to environmental sustainability but also to economic efficiency. Artificial stones, also known as synthetic marble, are particularly profitable composites that mimic natural ornamental stones. The practical preference for artificial stone over natural stone is based on technical advantages. For instance, the lower density of the polymeric matrix compared to natural stone gives artificial stone notable lightness. Additionally, artificial stones have fewer pores and flaws [3].

Artificially produced from high-strength resin, catalyst, and reinforcement, synthetic marble offers several advantages over natural marble. Notable features include high mechanical resistance, weather durability, hardness, the ability to withstand high temperatures, stain resistance, and excellent processability. Additionally, these materials have lower costs, design flexibility, and can exhibit both uniform colors and random variations, closely resembling natural stone. Synthetic marble can also be molded more easily, providing enhanced flexibility in the development of pieces such as bathtubs, countertops, and sinks [4].

Overall, the methods for artificial marble production are similar, involving the combination of the matrix, catalyst, and reinforcement. According to the literature, the most commonly used resins are acrylic, epoxy, and polyester. The catalyst initiates the polymeric reaction, while the reinforcement, often limestone and dolomite, enhances the material's properties. After mixing these components, the mass is poured into a mold, and the material is demolded shortly after the curing reaction is complete. Additional steps may be added to enhance mechanical properties, such as compaction, vibration, vibrocompression, microwave treatment, or the inclusion of a coupling agent in the mixture [5].

In this context, the present study aimed to develop synthetic marble pieces using mesquite wood ash as a filler in a polyester matrix. The ash was characterized for its mineralogical and granulometric composition, while the resulting material was characterized for its mechanical properties through compression and flexural tests. Thus, this work explains the materials and the method used for the production of the developed synthetic marble, presents the results and discussion, and concludes the study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The ash used in this study was sourced from Nossa Senhora do Carmo laundry in Caruaru, PE. This material was collected from the boiler ashtray at the facility and transported to the laboratory, where it was stored in sealed bags to minimize the effects of moisture and other external factors. During collection, it was noted that mesquite wood comprised 70% of the boiler's fuel, while the remaining 30% consisted of furniture residues and wood pellets. Therefore, the ash analyzed in this study represents the residue from the combustion of various organic materials.

The study employed uncured orthophthalic crystal unsaturated polyester resin that was pre-accelerated, fully polymerizable, with low reactivity and high viscosity, including UV absorbent properties and a gel time between 9 to 14 minutes. This resin, from the brand IBEX Chemicals and Composites, was used in its raw form. Methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP, C₄H₁₀O₄), known commercially as BUTANOX, was used as the initiator in its as-received state at room temperature, also from IBEX. Since polyester tends to adhere to mold surfaces, a release agent was essential. Carnauba liquid wax was used to facilitate the demolding process and ensure a smooth finish.

The sieve analysis was conducted according to ASTM C136:2019 specifications. The sieves used had the following openings: 4.75 mm, 2.36 mm, 1.18 mm, 600 μm, 300 μm, 150 μm, and 75 μm. For the test, 60 g of ash were weighed and placed on the sieves, which were then mechanically shaken at 15 Hz for 10 minutes. The amount of material retained on each sieve was individually weighed to determine the granulometric distribution.

In the absence of a standardized methodology in the literature, the compacted bulk density of the residue was assessed using the approach outlined by Cunha [7]. The following equipment was used: a 100 mL graduated cylinder, an electric shaker, and an analytical balance with a precision of 0.0001 g. First, the mass of the empty graduated cylinder was recorded. The ash was then added to the cylinder and shaken for two minutes at a frequency of 10 Hz to compact the residue. The ash was added until the cylinder reached the 100 mL mark, and the cylinder was weighed again. The bulk density was calculated using Equation 1, where ρ represents the bulk density of the compacted ash, m_1 is the mass of the empty container, m_2 is the mass of the container plus compacted ash, and V is the volume of the container.

The polymer concrete was prepared by mixing 40% by mass of unsaturated orthophthalic polyester resin with 60% by mass of wood ash. To initiate the curing process, 1% by mass of MEKP catalyst

relative to the combined mass of resin and ash was used. Preliminary tests determined the optimal proportions, which varied from 15% to 45% resin. Mixtures with 15%, 20%, and 25% resin crumbled post-curing as the resin was absorbed by the high porosity of the ash. Mixtures with 30% and 35% resin resulted in a dry mass with incomplete encapsulation of the reinforcement phase. The 40% resin mixture exhibited good workability, with the particulate phase fully enveloped by the matrix and withstood a 1-ton load during curing. The 45% resin mixture exhibited good workability, with the particulate phase fully enveloped by the matrix and withstood a 1-ton load during curing. The 45% resin mixture became overly fluid, overflowing under the 1-ton load applied during curing (as depicted in Figure 1). Thus, the optimal proportions for polymer concrete manufacturing in this study were 40% mesquite wood ash and 60% resin.

Figure 1: Mixture made with 45% resin and

Figure 2: Mixture with 40% resin poured into the metal mold

The ash (40% by mass) and resin (60% by mass) were measured separately. The catalyst amount (1% by mass of the total ash and resin) was calculated based on these measurements. In a 500 mL beaker, the resin and catalyst were mixed for about 2 minutes. Subsequently, the ash was added and mixed for approximately 3 minutes until homogeneous. Carnauba wax was applied as a mold release agent in a 100 x 100 x 10 mm³ metal mold, into which the mixture was poured (illustrated in Figure 2). The mold was then closed and subjected to a constant pressure of 1 ton in a hydraulic press for 24 hours (as shown in Figure 3). This pressure removed air trapped during mixing to ensure better mechanical properties of the material post-curing. After demolding, the polymer concrete slab (shown in Figure 4) was cut to the dimensions specified for compression, flexural, and apparent density tests.

Figura 3: Moldagem do concreto polimérico;

Figura 4: Placa de concreto polimérico após a desmoldagem

The mineralogical composition of the ashes was obtained using an X-ray diffractometer from Bruker brand, model D8 Advance, CuK α radiation, current of 40 mA, tube voltage of 40 kV, and scanning range of 5–80° with step size of 0.02° per second

For the determination of the apparent density of the composite produced in the present work, ten specimens of 50x50x14mm were used, following the Brazilian standard NBR 15845-15. The samples were saturated in deionized water was added up to 2/3 of the height of the samples, and after another four hours, more water was added until the samples were completely submerged. After 40 hours, the saturated mass (M_{sat}) and the submerged mass (M_{sub}) were determined. For the determination of the dry mass (M_{dry}), the samples were dried in an oven at 60°C until a constant mass was reached and then weighed. The apparent density of the composite was calculated using Equation 2.

$$\rho_a = \frac{M_{dry}}{M_{sat} - M_{sub}} \times 1000 \quad (2)$$

For the compression strength test, 5 specimens with dimensions of 12.5 x 12.7 x 25.4 mm³ were used, as specified in ASTM D 695 [8] standard, as illustrated in Figure 5. The specimens were subjected to compressive force using a Time Group INC- WDW-50E universal testing machine, with a maximum capacity of 1000 KN, at room temperature, as shown in Figure 6. The stress was calculated according to equation 3, where P represents the maximum breaking force and A is the initial area of the specimen face subjected to the load.

The three-point flexural strength test was conducted in accordance with the standard ASTM D790-17 [9]. For this test, five samples with dimensions of 100 x 25 x 10 mm³ were used, the specimens were subjected to bending force using the Time Group INC-WDW-50E type universal testing machine at room temperature, as shown in Figure 7. For this test, the beams were placed under the lower (reaction) and upper (action) blades, where the load was applied slowly at a rate of 1.19 mm.min⁻¹ until failure. Equation 3 was used to calculate the bending force, where P is the maximum breaking force, L is the span length of the tested piece, b is the width of the beam, and d is the thickness of the tested beam, as shown in Figure 8.

$$\sigma = \frac{3PL}{2bd^2} \quad (3)$$

Figure 5 Samples for compression test

Figure 6: Compression test

Figure 7: Samples for bending test

Figure 8: Bending test

III. RESULTS

From the diffractogram presented in Figure 9, it is possible to observe that the peak at $2\theta = 29.6^\circ$ is identified as a characteristic and more intense peak, as mixed biomass ash is a material with multiphase mineralogical composition, a significant number of peaks related to the calcium carbonate phase (CaCO_3) stands out, in addition, silicon dioxide (SiO_2) is present as a representative phase of the material.

The elevated quantity of calcium carbonate may be associated with the amount of calcium oxide in the material, and the presence of silicon dioxide is related to the crystalline phase of silica (quartz) [10,11]. The XRD pattern found is similar to those obtained by Nascimento [12], Pires [13], and Lima [14], who used mesquite wood ash in their studies. It is important to highlight that the diffractogram obtained by Nascimento [12] also showed crystalline phases of KCl and MgO, which were also observed in the present analysis, confirming the similarity between the residues.

Figure 9: X-ray diffractogram of mesquite wood ash

Table 1: Granulometric composition of the tested ash.

Mesh openings	Retained mass (g)	Retention percentage (%)	Accumulated retention percentage (%)	Passing percentage (%)
4.75 mm	11.1551	18.59	18.59	81.41
2.36 mm	4.3675	7.28	25.87	74.13
1.18 mm	2.7582	4.60	30.47	69.53
600 μm	5.0254	8.37	38.84	61.16
300 μm	7.4118	12.35	51.19	48.81
150 μm	6.8107	11.35	62.54	37.46
75 μm	17.8984	29.83	92.37	7.63
Bottom	4.5767	7.63	100	0

Following the sieving process, the results shown in Table 1 were obtained. It was found that the material collected from the boiler ash pit contained approximately 62.54% wt of impurities. According to Senger [15], these impurities are likely due to wood residues that did not fully combust and passed through the equipment grates along with the ash. The maximum characteristic dimension recorded with the CBM was 2.36 mm, matching the value reported by Leloup [16]. Borloni et al. [10] noted that traditional methods for determining particle size distribution are not ideal for ash, as ash often forms sintered clusters rather than discrete particles. Consequently, the particle size distribution curve may not accurately reflect individual ash particles. Nevertheless, the sieving test was crucial for this study, as it allowed for the selection of the particle sizes used in composing the particulate phase of the composite. Figure 10 illustrates the results of the test, showing the separation of the material based on its granulometry.

Figure 10: Sieved ashes separated according to their particle size

Table 2 Values used for the calculation of compacted unit density of ash, ash density, composite density, natural marble density, and resin density.

Mass of the empty graduated cylinder	0.0753 kg
Mass of the empty graduated cylinder + ash	0.1562 kg
Volume of the graduated cylinder	0.0001 m ³
Ash density	809±40 kg.m⁻³
Composite density	1500±0.04 kg.m⁻³
Density of natural marble [17]	~2715 kg.m⁻³
Density of polyester resin [18]	~1200 kg.m⁻³

Table 2 displays the measurements for the compacted unit mass of the ash. It is evident that the ash exhibits a low density, which likely contributes to the overall reduced density of the composite, given that the composition includes 60% wt ash. The synthetic marble produced in this study has a density of 1500 kg/m³, compared to approximately 2715 kg/m³ for natural marble [17]. This lower density in synthetic marble offers a notable advantage over natural marble. Much of this density difference can be ascribed to the low density of the ash used as reinforcement. Additionally, the matrix phase of the composite also has a relatively low density. According to Brisco [18], polyester resin has a density around 1200 kg/m³, significantly lower than that of natural marble.

The obtained value for compressive strength was 55 ±1 MPa, as shown in Table 3. This result is close to the findings of Bejan and Barbuta [19], who reported results ranging from 58 to 86.4 MPa. However, the present synthetic marble exhibits considerably higher values than those found by Sung and Kin [20], who reported values between 18.2 and 24.5 MPa, and lower than the results of Singla and Chawla [21], who found values between 84.3 and 102.3 MPa. It is important to note that authors who obtained considerably higher values than those in this study used techniques to enhance the mechanical properties of the material, such as vibration, compression, and vacuum, or, in some cases, a combination of all three techniques.

The obtained value for flexural strength was 15.0±0.4 MPa, as also shown in Table 3. The result obtained in this research is similar to values found in the literature, Ribeiro et al [22]. the result obtained by Sung and Kim [20], who found values between 6.4 and 8.4 MPa, is considerably lower than that of the synthetic marble developed in this study 15 MPa. Thus, the difference in values found may be related to the proportion of matrix phase used, considering the good flexural strength of polymers. This study used 40% of polymeric resin, while works found in the literature used between 10 to 15% of matrix phase.

Table 3: Results of mechanical test.

Author	Resin percentage (%wt)	Resin	Reinforcement	Compression test (MPa)	Bending test (MPa)
This work	40	Orthophthalic unsaturated polyester	ash	55±1	15±0.44
Herianto; Pahlevani; Sahajwalla [23]		Commercial natural stone		52	12.8
Herianto;		Commercial artificial stone		169	53.8

Pahlevani; Sahajwalla [23]					
Gomes et al. [24]	8	Epoxy	Granite	-	33
Silva; Ribeiro; Rodriguez [25]	-	Epoxy	Calcitic marble	69.39-95.89	30.5-37.42
Borselino; Calabrese; Di Bella [26]	20-40	Polyester - Epoxy	Calcitic marble residue	-	10.6-30.7
Ribeiro et al. [23]	15	Orthophthalic unsaturated polyester	Marble residue	81	15

IV. CONCLUSION

Synthetic marble pieces were obtained using a ratio of 40% crystal orthophthalic unsaturated polyester resin and 60% carob wood ash. The analysis of the unit mass confirmed the low density of the composite's reinforcing phase, as well as the low density of the synthetic marble developed in this study compared to natural marble. Thus, the low density of the synthetic marble produced in this work may be attributed to the low density of the ash. The determination of the ash's particle size distribution aided in understanding the material's granulometry used as particulate filler in the polymer matrix composite. Mechanical tests showed that the performance of the material produced is similar to those reported in the literature, especially in comparison to natural marble. This confirms that the developed material has potential for application as ornamental stone in the construction sector.

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